

IN-HABIT - INclusive Health And wellBeing In small and medium size ciTies

D8.5 COMMUNICATION ACTIONS REPORT I

Project Number	869227	Acronym	IN-HABIT
Full Title	INclusive Health And wellBeing In small and medium size ciTies		
Project URL	https://www.inhabit-h2020.eu/		
Document Type and Name	Deliverable, D8.5, Communication Actions Report I		
Project Coordinator	University of Cordoba		
Project Call and Funding Scheme	SC5-14-2019 - Visionary and integrated solutions to improve well-being and health in cities H2020-SC5-2019-2 (IA)		
Date of Delivery	M12 – Date 31/08/2021		
WP, WP Leader	WP8, BOT		
Status	Final		
Dissemination level (confidentiality)	Other/public/report		
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VERSION HISTORY

Version	Status	Date	Contributor/partner	Summary of changes
V 0.1	Draft	24/08/2021	BOT	Initial drafting
V 0.2	Draft	30/08/2021	BOT	Final draft
V 0.3	Final document	31/08/2021	BOT	Feedback included, language final revision

LIST OF ACRONYMS

D	Deliverable
DECO	Dissemination, Exploitation, Communication & Outreach
DC	Dissemination & Communication
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
GDEI	Gender, Diversity, Equity, Inclusion
H2020	Horizon 2020 projects
IHW	Inclusive Health and Wellbeing
KLC	Key Local Contact

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KPI	Key Performance Indicators
LCA	Local Community Activator
NBS	Nature Based Solutions
PC	Project Coordinator
PP	Project Partner
SMSCs	Small and medium sized cities
T	Task
WP	Work Package

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable summarizes the dissemination and communication activities related to project activities and results carried out by IN-HABIT partners during the last 12 months, since the project kick-off in October 2020 up to the project mid-term in September 2021.

The structure of the document responds to the WP8 - Dissemination and Communication tasks distribution specified in the Description of Actions (DoA). The distribution of tasks is as follows:

T 8.1. Dissemination & Communication Strategy;

T 8.2. Communication & Engagement Actions and Tools;

T 8.3. Dissemination Actions and Tools.

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1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Deliverable description

Work Package 8 (WP8) is focused on the communication and dissemination of IN-HABIT goals and BOT, as communication leader, coordinates this task at a consortium level. To accomplish this objective, the first task to complete was to build a main communication strategy, which has been defined and shared with all partners and submitted in M6 (D 8.1, Dissemination and Communication Plan).

BOT monitors the frequency of general communication around the project, establishing a connection between general communication and local one in the cities where the project is taking place, including the evolution in terms of dissemination, leading to the overall fulfilment of the objectives and the tasks defined in WP8.

To multiply the impact on the people involved and enlarge the community reached by this effort, IN-HABIT has developed an in depth analysis of the interested stakeholders, including sister projects (clustering activities), related organizations and local stakeholders, to engage them in the promotion of IN-HABIT's news and development. Hence, a wide and effective dissemination of results has been planned as one of the strong components of the project and all partners are committed to contribute.

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2. T 8.1. Dissemination & Communication Strategy

2.1. Start up

During the first year of the IN-HABIT timeline in WP8, a set of tools, methodologies and communication flows addressing the external and internal audience have been thoroughly selected and tailored to the context, considering the existence of a main objective, and multiple secondary goals specifically defined according to different local, national and European levels, diversity of targets or the level of interaction sought.

In particular, D 8.1. carried on from M1 to M6 included:

- Dissemination and communication plan;
- Communication guidelines;
- Project visual identity: logo, graphic concept, colours, head letters, layouts - slides, postcards and press releases;
- Dissemination actions - institutional and global outreach.

All tools have been widely shared with Project Partners (PPs), considering suggestions and possibilities of amelioration whenever possible, through surveys, dedicated meetings, and training, in order to foster inclusion and a collaborative, co-design approach that is key to the project.

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2.2. Dissemination and communication plan (DECO) and Communication Guidelines

The DECO plan has been developed by M6, using a comprehensive approach, including a general strategy for the overall project, and a tailor-made one on local needs and context, and internal & external communication guidelines.

BOT, in collaboration with the rest of partners, have produced the deliverable D 8.1 Communication and Dissemination Plan released in M6. This is a public document that summarizes the main guidelines to perform a quality communication of the project and its results, and specific measures to coordinate an efficient internal communication among the project partners, including a focus on the implementation of outreach activities. The DECO plan has taken into account the GDEI (Gender, Diversity, Equity and Inclusion) approach, as a unique and fundamental feature for project communication at all levels.

The document addresses the different aspects that a communication plan may focus on: the strategy from the project level to the external audience; the basis for a proper internal communication between the project partners; the elements needed to evaluate and measure the results of the communication strategy; and finally the obligations and constraints dictated by the EC regarding communication activities in every H2020 project.

The content of the document includes:

- General guidelines and toolkit;
- Communication stakeholders mapping;
- How to, dos and don'ts on visuals and general communication (channels, tone of voice, etc.);

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- Planned activities throughout the project.

The complete document will be available and open to the public on the IN-HABIT Website in the Deliverables section as soon as the deliverable is approved by the EC. In the meanwhile, the document and its shorter versions (video guides, guidelines and manuals) have been shared with PPs, and with the member of their teams dedicated to communication activities: communication referents identified by PPs by M5 for each partner; and Local Community Activators (LCA) and Key Local Contacts (KLC), identified in M6-M8 and playing an active role in communicating the project.

A DECO plan addendum for the cities, tailor-made on local specific needs after collecting them in local training (M7) led by project partner Tesserae (TSR), was integrated with the GDEI Toolkit by M10.

Other tools were developed in order for the PPs to run the project activities more smoothly and to support their communication activities:

- **Communication repository** for press and communication releases open to PPs. Public materials were also shared open access on the media section of the website. Available [here](#).
- **General toolbox** for PPs: a space dedicated to project communication where to retrieve communication guidelines, visual identities, templates and video guides. Available [here](#).
- **Informative Material:**
 - project leaflet (initial version in 5 languages - local languages and english), to be used to present the project in meetings and to inform the general public. A more structured, extensive version would be made available after M12 when data and research baseline material will be ready to be included. The leaflet is available [here](#).

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- project presentation: a general presentation for the general public, co-designed with all PPs (available [here](#)).

Fig. 1,2 - IN-HABIT general leaflet - English version

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Fig. 3,4,5,6 - IN-HABIT general leaflet - local versions

Communication guidelines were made available through the collaborative space above mentioned (General Toolbox).

2.4. Project visual identity

A complete project visual identity has been designed through a collaborative process. The idea is centralized on a clear IN-HABIT logo concept, including all the inputs received by project partners, and a colour pantone set. A complete set of potential logos was presented for discussion with the rest of project partners shortly after the Kick-Off meeting in M2 in order to choose the better one. Later on, the final logo was selected after various rounds of ameliorations and was the result of a co-design process.

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Fig. 7,8,9,10,11,12,13,14 - Initial IN-HABIT logo proposals

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Fig. 15 - IN-HABIT official logo

Internal support tools

Another important asset in terms of communication activity within the project is to provide homogeneous formats related to project deliverables, documents, presentations, or any other item eventually produced.

For this purpose, the project's visual identity and graphic package, including templates and communication guidelines were developed by M6. Different templates (in most known formats) were produced and made available for IN-HABIT partners: all these tools have been approved and are ready for use [here](#).

PRESENTATIONS TEMPLATE

- Formal presentation (for example, for external meetings, conferences and so on);
- Informal presentation (for internal meetings, etc.);
- Icon library (separated - for easier, lighter use).

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Templates were developed in two versions: lighter version, for download; complete version, for online use (like Teams, Drive or other collaborative spaces).

DOCUMENTS TEMPLATE

- Press release;
- Report;
- Meeting agenda;
- Meeting minutes;
- Deliverable;
- Letterhead;
- Simple document.

These templates were developed in 2 versions: Word (Office) version, downloadable, for offline work; Drive version, for documents needing collaborative approach and contribution from many partners, thus reducing the chance of errors. All of them have been tested to work properly on several devices.

IN-HABIT VISUAL IDENTITY GUIDE

This is a simple tool with examples of how to use logos and imagery, dos and don'ts. This how-to guide should be of help in supporting the PPs when visually expressing the project. It includes:

- **LOGOS** in the colours of the project palette, and black and white; both in high and low resolution.
- **PATTERNS** to be used as background designs for your communication as well.
- **FONT PACKAGE** to be downloaded to be consistent with the visual identity, although the chosen font is generally available on most systems

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- **EU Flag graphics** both in colour and black & white, including the project funding information.
- **ICONOGRAPHY** in the colours of the project palette, and black and white; both in high and low resolution.
- **FREE REFERENCE IMAGES** (for presentations)

Additionally, a [complete Guideline](#), including support videos, has been developed and shared among PPs in M7. It features:

- A video to better explain **visual identity tips**;
- A shorter video including a shorter version for **logo usage** for external collaborators;
- A **guidelines FAQ video** (following a survey among PPs).

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The IN-HABIT visual identity and graphic package includes:

VISUAL GUIDELINES

A simple tool with examples on how to use logos and imagery, along with dos and don'ts. This how-to guide will help creating consistent projects in line with the IN-HABIT brand.

OUR LOGOS

Our logos in the colours of the project palette, and black and white; both in high and low resolution.

OUR ICONS

Our icons in the colours of the project palette, and black and white; both in high and low resolution.

OUR PATTERN

Our patterns to be used as background designs for your communication.

NUNITO

OUR TYPOGRAPHY

Our typeface/font.

EU FLAG

The EU flag both in colour and black and white, including the project funding information.

IMAGES

Free images for you to use on your presentations.

Fig. 16- IN-HABIT template guideline

In order to establish a common visual line for all dissemination elements, a short version of the DECO plan, including a visual identity manual, was created, based on the Official IN-HABIT Logo shape and pantone, including fonts, sizes, additional logo variations, etc.:

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LIGHT BLUE

RED

YELLOW

GREEN

BLACK

WHITE

IN-HABIT BLUE

CMYK 78 24 0 8
 RGB 36 173 234
 HEX #24ADEA

IN-HABIT RED

CMYK 0 85 92 0
 RGB 239 68 65
 HEX #EF4441

IN-HABIT YELLOW

CMYK 00 00 00 00
 RGB 249 203 88
 HEX #F9CB58

IN-HABIT GREEN

CMYK 60 0 63 0
 RGB 53 229 149
 HEX #35E595

IN-HABIT FORMAL BLUE

CMYK 70 33 0 57
 RGB 33 173 109
 HEX #21496D

BLACK

CMYK 40 40 40 100
 RGB 0 0 0
 HEX #000000

WHITE

CMYK 0 0 0 0
 RGB 255 255 255
 HEX #FFFFFF

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NITRA (SLOVAKIA)

LIGHT BLUE

RIGA (LATVIA)

RED

CORDOBA (SPAIN)

YELLOW

LUCCA (ITALY)

GREEN

PRIMARY TYPEFACE

NUNITO

REGULAR

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
0123456789

BOLD

**ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
0123456789**

Fig. 17,18,19,20 - Extract from visual guidelines

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2.5. Communication Campaign

A roadmap towards the communication campaign envisaged for the project was established and shared among the PPs in the Steering Committee and Assemblies meetings.

In particular, one general campaign (presentation of the project) will be accompanied by four local focused campaigns where the IN-HUBs are established.

General campaign, postponed to end of September 2021 after consultation among the PPs and the PC, would have such characteristics:

- Focused on the project through an ‘institutional storytelling’ (description, objectives, values, PPs, evolution, results, research, links with global and European challenges, and also based on joint activities promoted in the institutional environment);
- Evaluate access of vulnerable groups and go digital in 2021 wherever outreach is possible.

Local campaigns, planned for Oct. 2021 to Mar. 2022 would have as main purposes:

- Bring out local storytelling, practices and results;
- Involve local groups giving new spaces for communication, debate and cooperation;
- Present best practices and results;
- Get public opinion’s and the decision makers’ attention;
- Represent the ongoing change;
- Return visibility to those who participate.

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A press office activity has been started, including a Press Office process locally and at a general level, the preparation of a Press kit and authorized contents, the organization of translations and local content, the research for outputs and informative material, finding out local channels used by institutions/service providers for primary information.

A roadmap has been developed as follows:

Institutional

What is IN-HABIT?
 Leaflet campaign
 Values: Nature and human being cooperation and wellbeing
 PP's interviews: our starting point research POV
 Work in progress in the Universities: PP's storytelling
 Values: GDEI in the project

03/06/2021

Local

What is IN-HABIT?
 Leaflet campaign in cities
 Interviews: our starting point, Cities POV
 Values: Nature+human being coop. and wellb. in the cities
 Values: GDEI in each city
 Work in progress in the cities: local storytelling
 Work in progress in the cities: local storytelling

Fig. 21 - Roadmap of communication campaigns

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A mapping of relevant activities, both at local and institutional level, has been carried out:

Institutional

contents for the diary at a general level
 social coverage
 press coverage
 press review
 PP's storytelling
 Updates from the institutional environment
 Update from the scientific environment
 OUR FIRST EVENT - joint activity with sister projects

Fig. 22 - Institutional campaign setting

Local

Local storytelling
 social coverage
 local media coverage
 local groups storytelling
 Updates from the local environment and institutions in each cities
 Updates and best practices in the IN-HUBS

Fig. 23 - Local campaign setting

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2.6. Dissemination actions - institutional and global outreach

Ongoing dissemination actions include:

- Participating in NBS Task force 4 on communication (joint strategies for communicating projects involving, among other objectives, Nature based solutions);
- Mapping stakeholders and institutional-relevant calendar for relevant ongoing initiatives;
- Participation in ongoing clustering activities with sister projects with the coordination of UCO to create synergies in communication and foster common actions.

2.7. Press activity

A launch press release (available [here](#)) has been issued by BOT at the beginning of the project (Kick off Meeting, October 2020) in five languages, and shared among all PPs. A press office activity was carried out to spread the news to relevant stakeholders shortly after, and local partners were invited to do the same in their local communities. A tracking tool (Communication Repository - available [here](#)) has been developed and shared among PPs, to include local press activities and reviews. Until the present time (M12), the project has seen:

- 14 published news from Cordoba (13 press or online articles, 1 TV report)
- 13 published news locally from Lucca (12 press or online articles, 1 radio report)
- 20 published news locally from Riga (19 press articles, 1 TV report)
- 13 general published news (international)

Once the first wave of press conferences/events has been organized by partners, BOT will elaborate a summary report, by merging the impact and hits of all of them.

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3. T 8.2. Communication & Engagement Actions and Tools

3.1. Communication material

On a first release, a short version in local languages was developed and shared with PPs on M7 (March 2021), and to be used in meetings and for local engagement purposes:

- 1 extended version in English published on the website, social media, and helpful as a reference for general audiences;
- 4 reduced versions in local languages, personalised for the 4 cities.

Both versions are in pdf format and already ready for online use and print. BOT used an A4 format and special attention to colour and readability to print it or fold it very easily in case you need to distribute it in meetings, even in black/white.

A project general presentation for general audiences has been completed with contribution of PPs and is available for use.

A more complete brochure, including innovations examples in cities, actions to be undertaken, and a focus on research and methodology is planned by the end of 2021.

Infographics, imagery and illustrations have been used to better convey important information.

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3.2. Website

The IN-HABIT website is the main information showcase of the project. The IN-HABIT website's main structure has been defined and confirmed and comprises two parts:

- A public area to raise awareness and guarantee the visibility of the IN-HABIT project, as well as to encourage the participation of stakeholders and inhabitants through the publication of project updates and news and the promotion of local initiatives. A reserved area that only project partners will be able to access in order to share files and useful documents that might not be open access.

All sections of the website feature the IN-HABIT logo in the top-left corner and the main contact information and indication of the funding received by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme at the bottom, in compliance with the European Commission guidelines on the matter.

A **site map** can be found at: <https://www.inhabit-h2020.eu/site-map/>

The ultimate goal is to produce a multilingual, user-friendly and easy-to-navigate space to enhance public awareness and promote local events, news and results through a recognisable and strong visual identity based on the project's communication guidelines, as long as a recognizable dynamic space to disseminate project progress and results.

The website represents a multilingual modular communication platform whose purpose is to be used by city partners to promote local visionary and integrated solutions (VIS), by disseminating project updates, news, events, results and products. The website will be integrated with the IN-HABIT platform and app and will embed social media news feeds throughout the project lifetime.

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After the confirmation and development of the visual identity of the project on M6, and following the first release of the landing page, feedback from PPs has been carefully collected during meetings with the communication representatives and through ad hoc surveys about the content and structure of the website. A survey among PPs was conducted before establishing the general architecture and for some choices in particular involving multilingual content.

A totally new, significantly improved version of the website, has been developed and shared with PPs in July 2021, taking into account their suggestions on a collaborative and collated feedback approach. The new website also responds to the suggestions of the project advisor (PA) and European Commission for a more dynamic, yet clear vehicle of information and dissemination.

The website can be reached at www.inhabit-h2020.eu and will be subject to regular updates as the project progresses.

Website efficiency is underpinned by the criteria of:

- Usability. Clear and accessible structure;
- Content updating;
- Accuracy in the content suitability.

The Web Site map has been designed to offer a complete overview of the project and an easy access to all its activities. The website main features are thoroughly described in D 8.3 (submitted at M6 for the landing page, and at M12 for the functioning website). This deliverable will be available on the website itself as soon as it is approved by the EC.

The current website map structure has been designed as follows and the public area comprises the following sections (pages and subpages):

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[Homepage](#)

[About](#)

[The project](#)

[Objectives](#)

[Roadmap/Work Plan](#)

[Outcomes](#)

[Cities](#)

[Cordoba](#)

[Lucca](#)

[Nitra](#)

[Riga](#)

[Partners](#)

[Project Partners](#)

[Sister projects](#)

[Resources](#)

[Media & Press](#)

[Scientific publications](#)

[Deliverables](#)

[Research activities](#)

[Newsletter](#)

[News & Events](#)

[News](#)

[Events](#)

[Reserved Area](#)

[Contacts](#)

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A password protecting PPs' access to the Reserved Area of the website has also been developed. This area centralizes the exchange of useful documents, not of public domain, among IN-HABIT PPs.

Analytics about the project website will be available in the next report, as it functioning version was just developed (July 2021).

Fig. 24 - IN-HABIT website, homepage

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Fig. 25 - IN-HABIT website - cities' pages

Fig. 26 - IN-HABIT website, resources page

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3.3. Social media and Storytelling

IN-HABIT Social Networks

Social media has become a very popular means of communication and disseminating information fast across heterogeneous target groups. These channels serve on-demand access to content anytime, anywhere, on any digital device. To extend the project target audience (specially to involve the great public and not only sector experts), IN-HABIT is integrating these media tools strategically in the communication and dissemination activities.

Twitter, LinkedIn and Facebook have been selected as the most appropriate social networks to promote the project achievements, news and outcomes so far. Instagram and Youtube will be added to the project accounts as soon as the training in communication for KLCs and LCAs are completed, allowing every city to be an ambassador of their own progress, also in local languages. An editorial plan for internal use was created. It contains the editorial strategy and the calendar of relevant events promoted by institutions, sister and clustering projects, and other Horizon 2020 projects that can be recalled in the IN-HABIT communication. The contents are currently scheduled two weeks before publication. PPs were asked to participate in this process, by mentioning relevant stakeholders and their channels, both globally and locally.

BOT, as a coordination leader, will act as a moderator of general social profiles, meaning controlling and filtering inadequate contents, and monitoring the suitability and relevance of the information to be published.

Accounts

- Facebook: <https://www.facebook.com/inhabith2020>
- LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/68868676/admin/>
- Twitter: https://twitter.com/INHABIT_H2020

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Official project hashtags have been shared, allowing to strengthen the communication and to focus on different project aspects of the innovations carried out, both at local and general levels:

- General: #Cityvolution #HumanSizeCity #INhabiTowns #innovatEU #EUinnovation
- Local: #EUforCordoba #EUforLucca #EUforNitra #EUforAgenskals #CordobaInnovative #LuccaInnovative #AgenskalnsInnovative #NitraInnovative #CityShareCulture #CityGrowsFood #GreenNewCity #CityCareForPets

| LINKEDIN |
|--|---|--|
| 207 people follow the page | 111 people follow the page | 81 people follow the page |
| 2-3 posts a week
53 posts in total (1/12- today)
5 videos | 2-3 posts a week
53 posts in total (1/12- today)
5 videos | 2-3 posts a week
53 posts in total (1/12- today)
5 videos |
| Posts media coverage:
Photos: 77
links : 72
Videos: 36 | Average of 4000 tweet impressions per month
Average of 400 visits to the profile per month | Average of 5 reactions per post
50 to 100 visualization per post |
| 3-4 of interaction per post | 3% to 10% engagement rate per tweet | Percentage of interest 15,72% |

Table 1 - Social media data up to M10

Training webinars

In collaboration with the project partner TSR, dedicated webinars on communication and press activities were conducted for LCAs in May 2021.

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In June and July 2021, dedicated webinars, addressing all communication referents but in particular LCAs and KLCs, have been held.

Regular follow-up meetings with LCAs are currently being held every two weeks, starting from M7. Regular meetings twice a month to tackle challenges and exchange ideas with KLCs have also been held from M7 onwards.

Specific meetings have been planned and carried out in June and July 2021, and dedicated webinars, addressing all communication referents but in particular LCAs and KLCs on:

- Promotional videos and highlights in cities to underline values and propositions;
- GDEI perspective with a practical approach with UREAD partner;
- Press, campaigning and required training on actions involved in the local campaign.

Partner's websites and social media

Some partners have regular newsletters, social media accounts and regular posts on their own websites. This activity will be used to disseminate the activities of the project regularly and frequently via these channels to complement the ongoing strategy.

3.4. Promotional Video

The promotional video will act, together with the website, as a window for the project. To better address the communication needs and targets, one promotional video about the project was produced in M10, to be combined with four short local teaser videos (to be used in launch campaign for local customised dissemination), to be finalized in M12, and produced in a co-design approach sharing the scripts and suggestions from PPs, especially local ones.

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Local videos will be subtitled in order to reach broader audiences locally.

3.5. IN-HABIT App

The IN-HABIT APP will be extremely simple and therefore innovative in its ease of use: like a friendly fellow citizen. The app will geolocate the users, entrust them with a role (tourist, citizen, young explorer, administrator), and communicate the following with them (PUSH):

- content by spatial proximity (you're close to something that interests you and maybe you're not aware of it), or conveyed by QR codes dotted around the city (photograph and receive);
- content by temporal proximity (an event next week; a discount for something useful);
- communications about activities, discounts, offers you're entitled to.

On the other hand, it will allow the user to communicate requests, report disservices etc. directly to the city administrations (PULL) and respond to surveys and/or behavioural games whose results and data (movement, activities, reading, consultations) on inhabitants' use of the city are delivered - in an anonymous form - to the administrators.

Discussion on initial technical requirements started with UCO and WTG partners in M5, following meetings with UREAD, ISIM, WTG, UCO, LCREA partners followed between M6-M9 to understand in particular:

- The aim of the app;
- Its application in correlation with the KPIs and needs expressed by the cities;
- Its feasibility in relation to the innovation actions undertaken in the cities.

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Main features and interactions of the app were discussed with PPs, the next steps will be to provide a list of functionalities for every city to choose from, combining them with missions to accomplish. Further open discussion with relevant partners and participation in meetings with the cities' representatives on the matter are to follow. The preliminary development is due on M22, and a testing period of six months in the cities will follow, until the delivery of the final version in M36.

4. T 8.3. Dissemination Actions and Tools

4.1. Meetings, events and digital approach

IN-HABIT partners collaborate in disseminating activities to their national and local audience, taking advantage of the close network they have in their own country. The IN-HABIT project was born in a year characterised by many changes that have revolutionised the uses, the possibilities of communication and social interaction and the working methods, impacting the ability of some events to have a prominent offline participation capable of generating exchange, affection, interaction and networking. The regulation resulting from the need to stem the COVID-19 pandemic has prevented demonstrations and events around the world from taking place, including the most important and symbolic ones. To date, it is not yet clear what will happen in the next year and if this will allow us to return to previous meeting and communication habits. However, what is certain is that the opportunity for offline events to be successful is also linked to people's trust in taking part, as well as the effective ability of those who promote and host them to guarantee safety conditions according to current regulations, taking on specific responsibilities, and local and national limitations and regulations about meetings and gatherings (i.e., limitations on number of people meeting, or adequate spaces) put in place by authorities.

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The unpredictability of events due to COVID-19 impacts the IN-HABIT project because it makes it more difficult to understand whether the physical events, which have objectives linked to the fundamental mission of the project (promoting inclusion, health and wellbeing), will be able to take place. In this phase of the project, however, it is important to be able to plan the organisation of such events also by evaluating the resources to be allocated that cannot be postponed. For this reason, to make planning more linear, a more digital approach to events has been proposed for 2021.

This choice presents the challenge of thinking of new ways to allow the participation of inhabitants and stakeholders in this project for which accessibility and inclusion are key values: many of the recipients of this project do not have access to digital devices (tablets and PCs) for various reasons and are at risk of being excluded. This plan will then illustrate how communication and project activities can be designed in an inclusive way by developing the approach to mainstream tools and channels and bringing project communication into containers and formats that are familiar and widespread among the targets, perhaps for other purposes (education, information, communication between peers, entertainment).

4.2. Dissemination KPIs

Communication activities are monitored according to a set of quantitative and qualitative success indicators. The evaluation of communication activities determines the degree to which the communication objectives have been reached, and the relationship between the outcomes and the efforts made to reach the goals. This analysis helps the project to better understand facilitators and barriers of a successful communication and serves to refine the communication activities accordingly. KPIs are currently in phase of monitoring and revision, and dedicated surveys will be conducted among PPs to monitor progress (i.e. workshops, local events, local

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dissemination activities, etc.) until the end of year 2021, taking into account the fact that many activities originally planned during Y1 have been postponed due to the pandemic situation and the consequent difficulties in selecting LCAs and the start up of their activities.

A set of KPIs has been specifically defined to monitor the successful deployment in terms of efficiency and effectiveness of dissemination activities. These indicators comprise:

Outputs/KPIs	Measurement Unit	Target Value	M12 KPIs
Project Website	-	1	1
App published	-	1	
Project Visual Identity	-	1	1
Project DECO strategy	-	1	1
City communication pack	Number of items	4	postponed
Policy guidelines for the replication of VIS that enhance IHW	-	1	
Replicable Business Model to boost IHW	-	1	
Project brochure	Number of items	5	5
Newsletters launched	Number of launches	50	
Press launch	Number of launches	10	1
Launch about IN-HUBs established in each city	Number of launches	4	
Co-designed workshop designed in each city	Number of workshops	8	
Business exploitation meetings	Number of business exploitation meetings	10	

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Presentation Video	Number of videos	1	
Video for local use	Number of clips	5	
Number of events attended as a guest	Number of events	10	
Number of events organised directly by the project (campaigns)	Number of events	5	
Scientific publications	Number of mentions	10	
Resources shared (informative material)	Number of resources	25	2 (leaflet, presentation)
External audiences of the website	Unique visitors	30,000	to be updated after M12 (functioning website)
Posts of dissemination on Facebook	Facebook Posts	500	53
Posts of dissemination on LinkedIn	Facebook	500	53
Tweets*	Number of tweets	100	53
Number on Facebook followers provided by the partners	Followers	3000	62 (not sponsored, provided by social media management activity by BOT)
Press release articles published by media and detected in the press review	Clip Articles of press review	200	62 (see pg. 22)
Dissemination activities by partners	Activities/partner	5	
Local events provided by partners	Number of local events/partner	10	
Activities of dissemination in IN-HABIT website on the pages of the cities*	Number of blog posts	20	
Number of events attended representing the project	Number of the events	10	
New volunteers/city	Number of volunteers/city	10	

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Number of local causes actively supported	Number of causes	5	
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Table 2 - IN-HABIT's communication KPIs

4.3. Communication and dissemination Mid-Term and Final Reports

Four different reports are envisaged in T 8.3, every 12 months until the end of the project (M60), when a final report is planned. These reports summarize the work done in terms of communication and dissemination activities.

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Fig. 7,8,9,10,11,12,13,14 - Initial IN-HABIT logo proposals

Fig. 15 - IN-HABIT official logo

Fig. 16 - IN-HABIT template guideline

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Fig. 17,18,19,20 - Extract from visual guidelines

Fig. 21 - Roadmap of communication campaigns

Fig. 22 - Institutional campaign setting

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Fig. 23 - Local campaign setting

Fig. 24 - IN-HABIT website, homepage

Fig. 25 - IN-HABIT website - cities' pages

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Fig. 26 - IN-HABIT website, resources page

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